

DETERMINANTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION STRATEGIES ON WHEAT (*Triticum aestivum*) PRODUCTION IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the assessment of climate change adaptation strategies on wheat production in Kano State, Nigeria. The study employed a multi-stage sampling technique to select 153 wheat farmers for the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics (multiple regression and Binomial test) were used to analyse the study's data. Results revealed that average age, household size, farm size and farming experience were 42.32 years, 7 persons, 4.12 ha and 13.93 years, respectively. The majority of farmers (77.12%) were willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies, with many farmers (46.41%) reporting moderate to very high effects of climate change on their wheat production. Adaptation strategies adopted to mitigate effects of climate change were: changes in planting (99.69%) and harvesting dates (97.37%), fertilizer application (94.12%), cropping system adjustments 89.54% and soil and water conservation practices (64.05%). Regression analysis revealed that five socio-economic factors, which were: age (b = coefficient -0.159, with a standard error (SE) of 0.012), education level (b = 0.322, SE = 0.059), household size (b = 1.367, SE = 0.001), farming experience (b = 4.219, SE = 1.843) and access to extension services (b = 1.205, SE = 0.117) significantly influenced farmers' willingness to adopt adaptation strategies. Furthermore, a binomial test confirmed a statistically significant difference between farmers willing (81.70%) and those unwilling (18.30%) to adopt climate change adaptation strategies, with a strong skew toward adoption. The study recommended that government and development agencies should design culturally sensitive programs that align with local customs to promote gender-inclusive farming that will encourage and support greater participation of women in agriculture generally and more specifically, wheat production.

Keywords: *Adaptation strategies, climate change, production, wheat farmers, adoption, willingness*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change poses a significant and growing threat to agricultural systems worldwide and this is manifested in the form of: reduced crop yields, water scarcity, increased pest and disease outbreak, extreme weather events, soil degradation, impact on livestock, food scarcity and livelihoods (Harshad *et al.*, 2024). The authors noted that crop productivity and agricultural livelihoods are already being impacted by rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall, and the growing occurrence of droughts, floods, and extreme weather events. Among staple crops, wheat is particularly susceptible to climate variability, owing to its sensitivity to temperature changes and water stress especially during key growth stages like flowering and grain filling (Shivalal *et al.*, 2024)

Wheat serves as a vital source of food and income for millions of smallholder farmers and plays a key role in national food security across many regions. However, research and findings of Grote *et al.* (2021) indicated that climate change has already contributed to yield declines in some parts of the world, with future projections warning of further losses if effective mitigation measures are not implemented. Buttressing further, Zi *et al.* (2020) stressed that, a 1°C increase in global temperature could result in a 6% decline in wheat production, which has serious implications for food supply, rural income, and socio-economic stability.

In response to climate change impacts, farmers are employing a range of adaptation strategies, including agronomic practices like altering planting schedules and crop rotation, adopting technological innovations such as drought-tolerant wheat varieties, implementing soil and water

conservation methods, and diversifying their livelihoods (Venu Prasad *et al.*, 2023). These approaches seek to reduce vulnerability, bolster resilience, and ensure sustained agricultural productivity in the face of changing climate conditions.

However, according to Antti *et al.* (2021) the uptake of these adaptation strategies differs widely across regions, communities, and individual farmers. Gaining insight into the factors that influence these decisions is crucial for promoting effective and inclusive climate-resilient agriculture. Key influencing factors may include: socioeconomic factors such as education, income, access to credit, etc; Institutional support like extension services, farmer organizations, and access to climate information; Environmental factors such as agro-ecological zone, soil type, and historical climate exposure. Although extensive research has explored climate change and its general effects on agriculture, there remains a notable gap in understanding the specific factors that drive the selection and adoption of adaptation strategies in wheat production (Mobeen *et al.*, 2025). This study is justified by the need to bridge this gap in knowledge.

Specific objectives of the study:

- i. Analyze the wheat farmers socio-economic characteristics in Kano States.
 - ii. Examine willingness of the farmers to adopt climate change adaptation strategies on wheat production in the area.
 - iii. Assess effects of climate change on level of wheat production
 - iv. Identify effective climate change adaptation strategies adopted by wheat farmers
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Hypotheses of the study:

- Hoi: Wheat farmers' willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies is largely independent of their socio-economic characteristics.
- Hoi: The proportion of farmers willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies for wheat production does not differ significantly from those unwilling to do so.

METHODOLOGY**Area of study**

The area of study is Kano State, located in North-West Nigeria at coordinates 11.74710° N and 8.52470° E. It comprises 44 Local Government Areas (LGAs), with Kano City serving as the State capital. As of 2022, Kano State has an estimated population of 15,462,200, making it the most populous state in Nigeria (National Population Commission, 2022). The state shares borders with Katsina to the northwest, Jigawa to the northeast, Bauchi to the southeast, and Kaduna to the southwest. The State is home to several major ethnic groups, including Hausa, Fulani, Beriberi (Kanuri), Tuareg, Arab, and Nupe, with Hausa being the predominant language spoken. Kano State is widely recognized as a hub of commerce, education, culture and Islamic education in northwestern Nigeria. Kano State is rich in mineral resources such as cassiterite, copper, glass sand, lead/zinc, gemstones, pyrochlore, and tantalite and the people are primarily agrarian in practice, with about 70% of the population engaged in agricultural activities. Though English serves as the official language, Hausa is predominant spoken language.

Sampling procedure and sampling size of the study

This study was carried out using multi-stage random sampling technique to select the respondents of the study. The process had to do with random selection of Kano Central and Kano South agricultural zones in the State (stage 1). This was followed by random selection of Fagge and Kano Municipal LGAs from Kano Central agricultural zones, while Rano and Tudun Wada LGAs were randomly selected from Kano South agricultural zones, thus making it 4 LGAs that were used for the study (stage 2). Stage 3 involved random selection of Sabon-Gari and Alfa towns from Fagge LGA while Kano Municipal and Albasa were randomly selected from Kano Municipal LGA. In the case of Rano LGA, Rano and Dawaki towns were randomly selected, while Dalawa and Samana were the randomly selected towns from Tudun Wada LGA. In all, 8 towns where wheat is known to be well cultivated were used for the study. It was from these towns 20 wheat farmers were randomly selected and this resulted to having 160 of them administered with the question instruments (stage 4). The number of farmers selected from each town because the focus was on farmers who were on solely farming wheat and not into mix-cropping. Out of 160 questionnaires administered, 153 valid responses were used for all analyses.

Validation of research instrument and source of data

Research instrument validity was ascertained through the use of face content method where experts were presented with the instruments for criticism to be sure it addresses the objectives and hypotheses of the study. Its reliability was assessed using

test-re-test method and the analysis produced correlation coefficient, $r = 0.65$ which by implication shows that the instrument was moderately reliable.

Primary data were used for the study and they were sourced from the wheat farmers.

Data analytical technique

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse data of the study. The former involved using percentage, mean, mode and standard deviation to analyse farmers socio-economic characteristics, their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies and effects of climate change on wheat production. Four-point Likert scale was used to analyse climate change adaptation strategies. The scale ranked from strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree, respectively coded as 4, 3, 2 and 1. It resulted to a mean weight

of 2.50. Adaptation strategies with mean score of ≥ 2.50 indicated that the farmers agreed that the factors were effective adaptation strategies of climate change. On the contrary, factors that have values that were < 2.50 implies otherwise.

Inferential statistics involved the use of Binary logistic regression model and Binomial test to analyse hypotheses one and two respectively. Hypothesis one, through Linear regression model analysed the influence of wheat farmers socio-economic characteristics on their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. This model explains the relationship between dependent (farmers willingness) and independent variables (socio-economic variables), typically expressed as:

$$\text{Logit}(P) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_9 X_9$$

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Where:

Y = Farmers willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies (Willing = 1; unwilling = 0)

β_0 = Constant

β_i [1 – n or 9] = Coefficients of independent variables

$X_1 - X_9$ = Independent variables

e = Error term

The variables in the model are specified below as;

Y = Farmers willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies (Willing = 1; unwilling = 0)

X_1 = Gender (dummy: male = 1; female = 0)

X_2 = Age (years)

X_3 = Education level (No formal educ. = 1; primary educ. = 2; sec. educ. = 3; post-sec. educ. = 4)

X_4 = Marital status (single = 1, married = 2, divorced = 3, widow(er) = 4)

X_5 = Farming experience (years)

X_6 = Farm size (measured in ha.)

X_7 = Household size (number of people living and feeding together)

X_8 = Access to credit (N)

X_5 = Access to extension services

Binomial test was used to analyse hypothesis 2 and it determined if farmers that are willing significantly differ from those not willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. The binomial distribution formula is presented below:

$$b(x;n,p) = nC_x * p^x * (1-p)^{n-x} \text{ ----- (Eq. 1)}$$

where; b = binomial probability;

x = total number of farmers (willing and unwilling to adopt climate change adaptation strategies for wheat production).

p = probability of success on an individual trial; n = number of trials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, as presented in Table 1, show that the majority of wheat farmers (71.90%) were male, while females constituted a smaller proportion (28.10%). This suggests that wheat farming in the area is predominantly male-dominated, likely influenced by cultural and religious practices. Specifically, the prevalence of Islam and the observance of purdah which encourages women to remain within the household may limit female participation in farming activities (Inyang *et al.*, 2025). Findings of Ndanitsa *et al.* (2021) corroborated this result, noting that in Muslim-dominated regions, farming activities are typically men's activities. The age distribution of the farmers revealed that the largest group (37.90%) fell within the 40–49-year range, with an average age of 42.32 years. This suggests that wheat farmers in the area are relatively young and likely possess the energy and capacity to effectively engage in agricultural activities. A similar age pattern was reported by Ndanitsa *et al.* (2021) in a nearby region, where it was concluded that farmers within this age group have the physical strength and potential to achieve significant success in farming. The farmers exhibited varying

levels of education, with the majority (57.52%) having attained primary education. This indicates that most farmers possess basic literacy skills, which are essential for understanding and applying climate change adaptation strategies in their agricultural practices. These findings are consistent with those of Okwuokenye *et al.* (2023), who also reported a predominance of farmers with primary school education in the same region. Results on marital status showed that the majority of farmers (65.36%) were married. This suggests that farming in the area is largely undertaken by married individuals, who are often regarded as responsible and likely to have dependents to support. This finding aligns with the observations of Okwuokenye *et al.* (2023), who reported a higher involvement of married individuals in farming, noting that they are typically the primary economic providers for their households. The average household size of farmers was 7 persons with the modal (45.10%) having 7 – 9 persons in their household. Findings thus indicated that, the respondents had a large house hold size which can suffice as family labour to the farmers. This assertion is backed by findings of Mairabo (2021) which supported the claim that farming in similar areas is dominated by farmers with large house hold size and could help to support the farmers farm operations. The

most common farm size among respondents (58.17%) ranged between 2 and 4 hectares, with an average farm size of 4.12 hectares. This indicates that the area is predominantly occupied by small-scale farmers. These findings are in tandem with Garba *et al.* (2021), who described the majority of farmers in Nigeria as operating on a small scale.

Average farming experience among wheat farmers was 13.93 years, with the largest proportion (36.60%) having between 15 and 19 years of experience. This indicates that the farmers are generally well-experienced in their agricultural practices. This finding agreed with Manda *et al.* (2020), who noted that farmers in Northern Nigeria typically possess substantial farming experience. Majority of the farmers (59.48%) reported having no access to credit, while a smaller proportion (40.52%) indicated access to at least one

source of credit. The lack of access implies that these farmers primarily rely on personal resources or self-financing to support their agricultural activities. This finding stands in contrast to the report by Akpomede (2023), which asserted that farmers receive financial support to carry out their farming operations. The data also showed that a significant majority of farmers (76.20%) had access to extension services. This suggests that the extension unit of the Ministry of Agriculture is effectively fulfilling its mandate of disseminating improved agricultural technologies to farmers. These findings corroborate those of Akpomede (2023), who emphasized that farmers benefit from access to extension services, particularly as a social advantage gained through participation in farmer groups.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents.

Socio-economic variables	Categories	Freq.	Percentage	Mean
Gender	Male	110	71.90	
	Female	43	28.10	
Age range (years)	< 30	21	13.73	
	30 – 39	42	27.45	
	40 – 49	58	37.90	
	50 – 59	21	13.73	
	60 and above	11	7.19	42.32 years
Educational Status	No formal Educ.	22	14.38	
	Primary Educ.	88	57.52	
	Secondary Educ.	31	20.26	
	Post-Secondary Educ.	12	7.84	
Marital status	Single	22	14.38	
	Married	100	65.36	
	Divorced	17	11.11	
	Widow(er)	14	9.15	
Household size	1 – 3	16	10.46	
	4 – 6	38	24.84	
	7 – 9	69	45.10	
	≥ 10	30	19.61	7.22 = 7 persons

Farm size (ha.)	< 2	15	9.80	
	2 – 4	89	58.17	
	5 – 7	31	20.26	
	≥ 8	18	11.76	4.12 ha.
Farm experience (years)	< 5	11	7.19	
	5 – 9	21	13.73	
	10 – 14	42	27.45	
	15 – 19	56	36.60	
	≥ 20	23	15.03	13.93
Access to credit	Yes	62	40.52	
	No	91	59.48	
Access to extension services	Yes	112	76.20	
	No	41	26.80	

Source: Field survey, 2024, N = 153

Farmers willingness to adoption of climate change adaptation strategies on wheat production

Table 2 presents farmers' willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies in wheat production. The results indicate that a majority (77.12%) expressed willingness to implement such strategies to mitigate the effects of climate change. In contrast, 13.73% were unwilling, and 9.15% remained undecided. Through

personal communication, many respondents expressed concern over the declining yields attributed to climate change and showed interest in receiving education on effective adaptation measures. These findings align with those of Ceesay *et al.* (2025), who also reported that farmers are generally willing to adopt various climate change mitigation strategies to address climate-related challenges.

Table 2: Farmers willingness to adoption of climate change adaptation strategies on wheat production.

Farmers willingness	Frequency	Percentage	Mode
Willing	118	77.12	
Not willing	21	13.73	
Undecided	14	9.15	
Total	153	100.00	Willing

Source: Field survey, 2024

Effects of climate change on level of wheat production

Table 3 presents the perceived effects of climate change on wheat production. A significant proportion of farmers (46.41%) reported that the effects were high, while 16.99% rated the impact as very high.

Additionally, 23.53% considered the effects to be moderate. On the other hand, 9.15% of respondents perceived the effects as low, and a small fraction (3.92%) indicated that climate change had no impact on their farming activities.

Table 3: Effects of climate change on level of wheat production

Effects of climate change on wheat production	Frequency	Percentage	Mode
- Very high	26	16.99	
- High	71	46.41	
- Moderate	36	23.53	
- Low	14	9.15	
- No effect	6	3.92	
- Total	153	100.00	High

Source: Field survey, 2024

Overall, a substantial proportion of farmers acknowledged that climate change has adversely affected their crop production in multiple ways. This finding is consistent with the observations of Marie *et al.* (2020), who reported that climate change has had a broad impact on farmers, especially smallholder producers who are highly dependent on agriculture for their livelihoods.

Effective adaptation strategies adopted by wheat farmers to mitigate effects of climate change

Effective climate change adaptation

strategies adopted by wheat farmers are summarized in Table 4, based on their relative frequency (in percentages). Strategies adopted by 50% or more of the respondents are considered key measures for mitigating the effects of climate change. Under the multiple-response format, the most commonly used or adopted strategies included changes in planting dates (99.69%), adjustments in harvesting dates (97.37%), fertilizer application (94.12%), alterations in the timing of land preparation activities (93.46%), and cropping system adjustments (89.54%).

Table 4: Effective adaptation strategies adopted by wheat farmers

Adaptation Strategies	Frequency	Percentage
- Changes in planting dates of crops	151	99.69*
- Changes in harvesting dates of crops	149	97.39*
- Fertilizer application	144	94.12*
- Alteration in timing of land preparation activities	143	93.46*
- Cropping adjustments systems	137	89.54*
- Inter-cropping system	135	88.24*
- Adoption of zero or minimum tillage system	131	85.62*
- Contour cropping across hill / slopes	117	76.47*
- Expansion of cultivated areas.	112	73.20*
- Planting new and improved crops varieties that can resist climate change	111	72.55*
- Afforestation	107	69.93*
- Practicing crop rotation system	106	69.28*
- Apply water management and irrigation systems	98	64.05*
- Practicing mixed cropping system	92	60.13*
- Make laws against deforestation activities	74	48.37

Source: Field survey, 2024; *Strategies that are popularly used by the respondents

Other effective adaptation strategies adopted by farmers included intercropping (88.24%), the use of zero or minimum tillage systems (85.62%), contour cropping across hills and slopes (76.47%), expansion of cultivated land (73.20%), and the adoption of new and improved crop varieties resistant to climate change (72.55%). Additionally, farmers practiced afforestation (69.93%), crop rotation (69.28%), water management and irrigation techniques (64.05%), and the cultivation of diverse crop types (60.13%). Iheke and Agodike (2016) supported these findings, noting that the identified adaptation strategies are effective in reducing farm losses, enhancing productivity and income, and strengthening farmers' resilience to climate change ultimately contributing to improved food security. Similarly, Ceesay et al. (2025)

agreed that these strategies play a vital role in helping farmers manage the impacts of climate change.

Relationship between farmers socio-economic characteristics and their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies

Table 5 presents results of the Binary logistic regression analysis examining the relationship between farmers' socio-economic characteristics and their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies in wheat production (hypothesis 1). The sample size was 153 respondents and the model included nine socio-economic variables, of which five were found to significantly influence farmers' willingness to adopt these strategies. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.611, with an F-value of 7.325,

indicating that approximately 61.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (farmers' willingness to adopt adaptation strategies) is explained by the model.

Among the socio-economic variables, age was found to be significant at the 1% level (p-value = 0.001) and negatively associated with farmers' willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. The coefficient was -0.159, with a standard error of 0.012 and a t-statistic of 3.201. This indicates that younger farmers are more likely to adopt adaptation strategies compared to their older counterparts. This finding is in line with the results of Haruna *et al.* (2022), who also reported age as a significant factor with a negative influence on the adoption of climate change mitigation strategies. The educational level of farmers had a positive coefficient of 0.322, with a standard error of 0.059 and a t-statistic of 1.961, indicating significance at the 5% level (p-value = 0.012). This suggests that farmers with higher levels of education are more likely to be willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. This finding is consistent with Donkoh *et al.* (2019), who reported that educational attainment positively influences farmers' willingness to adopt climate change mitigation measures.

Household size had a positive coefficient of 1.367, with a standard error of 0.001 and a t-statistic of 2.782, indicating a statistically significant relationship at the 1% level (p-value = 0.011). This suggests that farmers with larger households are more likely to adopt climate change adaptation strategies, likely due to the greater availability of family labor. This finding is consistent with the study by Atube *et al.* (2021), which

found that larger households had a higher likelihood of adopting climate change measures compared to smaller ones. Farming experience had a coefficient of 4.219, with a standard error of 1.843 and a t-statistic of 3.002, indicating a positive and statistically significant relationship at the 1% level (p-value = 0.021). This suggests that farmers with more years of experience are more likely to adopt climate change mitigation strategies. The finding is consistent with the study by Amare *et al.* (2018), which reported that increased farming experience enhances the likelihood of adopting improved agricultural practices. Access to extension services was found to be significant at the 5% level (p-value = 0.041), with a coefficient of 1.205, a standard error of 0.117, and a t-statistic of 2.587. The positive relationship suggests that farmers who have access to extension services are more likely to adopt climate change mitigation strategies, as they receive guidance and information from extension agents that enhance their capacity to address climate-related challenges. This result is supported with the findings of Niles *et al.* (2016) who observed that farmers who had more contacts with extension services were those ready to adopt adaptation strategies. Okwuokenye and Okoh (2024), who emphasized that access to extension services improves farmers' knowledge and preparedness in managing the effects of climate change.

Table 5: Relationship between socio-economic characteristics and farmers willingness to adopt climate change mitigation strategies

Socio-economic variables	Coefficient	Standard error	T-statistic	P-value
Constant	0.486	0.219	5.638	
Gender	2.0183	1.902	0.674	0.124
Age	-0.159	-0.012	3.201**	0.001
Educational level	0.322	0.059	1.961*	0.012
Marital status	0.234	0.201	1.502	0.302
Household size	1.367	0.001	2.782**	0.011
Farm size	2.623	1.782	1.341	0.114
Farming experience	4.219	1.843	3.002**	0.021
Access to credit	1.323	0.994	1.258	0.133
Access to extension services	1.205	0.117	2.587*	0.041
R^2 – value	0.643			
Adjusted R^2	0.611			
F – value	7.325			

* $P \leq 0.05$; **Significant at 1% level; *Significant at 5% level

Difference between farmers that are willing and those not willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies

The difference between farmers that are willing and those not willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies was analysed using Binomial test (hypothesis 2) and the results presented in Table 6. Results from analysis showed that most (81.70%) of farmers showed their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies while the other fraction (18.30%) indicated their unwillingness to adopt the strategies. From result presented, wheat farmers response was skewed and significant at the

1% level towards their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. It was based on these findings that the alternative hypothesis, suggesting that: proportion of farmers that are willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies for wheat production differ significantly from those unwilling to adopt was accepted, rejecting the null hypothesis. The result runs in agreement with those of Ceesay *et al.* (2025), who also observed that farmers are generally willing to adopt a range of climate change mitigation strategies to cope with climate-related challenges

Table 6: Difference in farmers that are willing and those not willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies

Level of farmers willingness	Frequency	Proportions	Prob. Level
Willing	125	0.817	0.001
Not willing	28	0.183	
Total	153	1.000	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the socio-economic characteristics of wheat farmers and their willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies. The findings revealed that wheat farming in the study area is largely male-dominated (71.90%), with most farmers falling within the productive age range of 40 – 49 years. The majority (57.52%) had attained at least primary education, were married (65.36%), and had relatively large household sizes (45.10%), which likely contribute to the availability of family labour for farming. Farm sizes averaged 4.12 hectares, indicating a predominance of small-scale farming, and farmers had considerable farming experience, averaging nearly 14 years. While access to extension services was relatively high (76.20%), access to credit remained limited, with most farmers relying on personal resources for financing their agricultural activities. The results further showed that a significant majority of farmers (77.12%) were willing to adopt climate change adaptation strategies and Climate change was perceived to have a substantial impact on wheat production, with many farmers ((46.41%) reporting moderate to very high effects. In response, a wide range of adaptation strategies were adopted, including changes in planting (99.69%) and harvesting dates (97.37%), fertilizer application ((94.12%), cropping system adjustments 89.54%) and soil and water conservation practices (64.05%).

Regression analysis revealed that five socio-economic factors, which were: age (coefficient was -0.159, with a standard error of 0.012 and a t-statistic of 3.201), education level (coefficient of 0.322, with a standard error of 0.059 and a t-statistic of 1.961), household size (coefficient of 1.367, with a standard error of 0.001 and a t-

statistic of 2.782), farming experience (coefficient of 4.219, with a standard error of 1.843 and a t-statistic of 3.002), and access to extension services (coefficient of 1.205, a standard error of 0.117, and a t-statistic of 2.587) significantly influenced farmers' willingness to adopt adaptation strategies. Notably, younger, more educated, experienced farmers with larger households and better access to extension services were more likely to adopt such strategies. Furthermore, a binomial test confirmed a statistically significant difference between farmers willing (81.70%) and those unwilling (18.30%) to adopt climate change adaptation strategies, with a strong skew toward adoption.

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were reached;

Recommendations

- i. Given the male-dominated nature of wheat farming in the study area which was largely influenced by cultural and religious norms, government and development agencies should design culturally sensitive programs that align with local customs to promote gender-inclusive farming that will encourage and support greater participation of women in agriculture generally and more specifically, wheat production.
 - ii. Since the majority of farmers have at least primary education and have shown willingness to adopt climate change adaptation strategies, targeted educational campaigns, extension training, and farmer field schools should be developed to help build knowledge on specific adaptation techniques, that would
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- complement the farmers residual skills and knowledge on adoption strategies.
- iii. The positive impact of extension services on farmers' willingness to adopt adaptation strategies underscores the need for increased investment by government and other stakeholders in upscaling employment, development and deployment of extension agents that would provide readily and accessible services on specific climate challenges as faced by wheat farmers, and;
 - iv. Since a significant number of farmers seemed to be lacking access to credit, there is an urgent need by government through her Ministry of Agriculture, develop farmer-friendly credit schemes, including interest-subsidized loans, cooperative financing models, and microcredit services that can enable investment in climate-resilient technologies and practices by the farmers.

Competing Interests: The Author declare that there is no conflict of interest

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